

**MIDWIVES' POPULATION: A VERITABLE TOOL FOR INTRAPARTUM CARE
SERVICE PROVISION AT PRIMARY HEALTH CENTRES IN
CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine midwives' population and its effect on the provision of intrapartum care services at Primary Health Care level in Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve this objective, three research questions and one hypothesis was postulated to guide the study. The research design adopted for the study was the survey design. The sample comprised of 70 midwives selected through the use of census sampling technique. A questionnaire titled "Midwives Population and Intrapartum Care Service Questionnaire" was used to collect data for the study. Simple percentages and the t-test statistical analysis was employed to test the hypothesis at 68 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance. The result indicated that the one PHC that has above 3 midwives render high quality care services to client than the 43 PHC that have below 3 midwives' population. Results showed a statistically significant difference between midwives' population and intra-partum care service provision at PHC in Cross River State. This implies that there is a significant relationship between midwives' population and intrapartum care service delivery in PHCs in Cross River /State, Nigeria. Based on this finding, it was recommended that the presence of midwives in State Primary Health Care Development Agency should be strengthened. Nursing and midwifery council should review the policy to establish community midwifery in Cross River State where more midwives will be trained and automatically employed to PHC level in the State.

(Keyword= Midwives' Population, Intrapartum, Care, Service Provision, Primary Health Centres)

INTRODUCTION

Nursing and midwifery services are a vital resource for attaining health and development targets as they form the backbone of health systems around the globe through the provision of a platform for consolidated efforts towards tackling diseases and ill-health. If we are to succeed in improving health systems performance, urgent action is needed to overcome the problems that seriously undermine the contribution these services can make to the vision of better health for all communities (World Health Organization, 2002). Researchers who modeled the projected effects of scaling-up midwifery predicted that a ten percent increase in coverage of midwifery-led care would result in a twenty-seven percent reduction in maternal mortality in low and middle income countries (UNFPA, ICM and WHO 2014).

The major roles of midwives include rendering care to women during pre-pregnancy, pregnancy, intra-partum and postpartum periods. Overall, this care aim towards positive outcome in the process of childbearing for both mother and baby (International Confederation of Midwives, 2005; Masterson, 2010). Furthermore, midwifery services extend to the client's family and the larger community (ICM, 2005). The World Health Organization classifies midwives as skilled birth attendants alongside with doctors and nurses with midwifery skills (WHO, 1999). This implies that midwives are very important in the reduction of maternal mortality. As opined by De Brouwere, Tonglet & Larberghe, 2002; and Henry, et al, 2017), a strategic approach by WHO towards reduction in maternal mortality is skilled birth attendance in addition to Emergency Obstetric Care (EmOC) and community mobilization

Until recently, records have indicated that there were about 240,000 qualified nurses and midwives within the country. However, Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria using more accurate information from OpenSource Human Resources Information Solution (OHRIS) reported that the actual number of those registered to be about 136,000. The OHRIS Qualify data thus indicated that there are far fewer nurses and midwives available than expected to provide much-needed health services to Nigerians (Sunday & Etuk, 2024). Additionally, given limitations in available workforce data within the country, the council's data on active registration remain the most reliable proxy for determining the combined number of qualified and available nurses and midwives in

Nigeria, across both the public and private sectors (Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN), 2012; Eneyo et al, 2022; Sunday et al, 2025).

In 2006, the World Health Organization's World Health Report identified 57 countries facing a critical shortage of health workers that is those with fewer than 2.3 doctors, nurses, and midwives per 1,000 populations. Against that ratio, Nigeria reported a shortage of nearly 40,000 health workers. The new data indicate that Nigeria's shortage of midwives is closer to 144,000, over three times the number reported in 2006.

This would be comprised of 70 bound registers containing information on 19 different cadres of nurses and midwives. Statistical information was generated manually and compiled into reports using Excel (Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria [NMCN], 2012).

Maternal mortality remains a major public health challenge globally, with an estimated 295,000 annual maternal deaths. This high global prevalence is attributed to mortality from low- and middle-income countries especially sub-Saharan Africa which accounts for 66.3% of all maternal deaths compared to 5% in developed countries. The high prevalence in sub-Saharan Africa is secondary to poor access to maternal and child health services. Nigeria, one of the largest countries in sub-Saharan Africa accounts for 15% of all maternal deaths globally and a maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 917 per 100,000 live births (WHO et al, 2019; Orokpo et al, 2024). Cross River which is one of the states in South-Eastern Nigeria tops the list for high maternal mortality in the country with MMR of 2000 per 100,000 live births (NDHS, 2013).

According to Esuabana (2020) and Sunday et al (2025), the reason for this alarming ratio is presumed to be that antenatal, delivery and postnatal services are mostly provided by traditional birth attendants (TBAs), and faith-based institutions without skilled attendants at birth accounting for only 41.3%. (NDHS, 2013). The close correlation between access to a skilled, motivated, and supported midwife and maternal and child health is well established (Roskam, et al. 2011). Worldwide however, there is an estimated shortage of 4.3 million midwives, nurses, and doctors, with the shortage most severe in low- and middle-income countries (Roskam et al 2011; WHO, 2006). Meanwhile, research indicates that teams of midwives and midwife assistants working in facilities could increase coverage of maternity care by up to an additional 40% by 2015 (Koblinsky, et al, 2006).

The availability of skilled health providers (particularly midwives) is critical in ensuring high quality ante natal, intra-partum, emergency obstetric and post-natal services. Indeed, SDGs for maternal health is unlikely to be achieved without attention to the recruitment and retention of midwives as averred by WHO, 2017; ICN, 2017; Esuabana, 2019; Sunday & Neji, 2023. Accelerating progress towards the SDGs and pursuing an ambitious post-2030 development agenda will require governments, civil societies and professional associations to work with educational institutions, NGOs and a range of international and bilateral organizations to ensure that midwives are more actively sought and retained, and that the value of existing staff is better recognized, to avoid the risk of a post-2030 slow-down (WHO, 2012; Sunday, 2025).

As part of the effort to achieve universal health coverage (UHC) in Nigeria, the Cross River State Ministry of Health (CRSMOH) recently conducted an orientation for health workers on the need to encourage women adoption of National Self-care/Self-injection plan. The training in Calabar, Cross River state was facilitated with technical support from the Federal Ministry of Health, the World Health Organization (WHO) and partners. The main objective was to strengthen access to self-care/self-injection innovation in Nigeria and to educate frontline health care workers on the self-care guidelines for sexual reproductive health. Emphasis was on the scale-up of Depot-medroxyprogesterone acetate (DMPA-SC) self-injection, yet maternal mortality still persist (Sunday, 2025).

Recently, Cross River State Primary Health Care Development Agency and the World Health Organization (WHO) stated that the state needs 784 (seven hundred and eighty-four) midwives across the 18 Local Government Areas with at least four midwives per ward, as declared during the International Day of the Midwife (IDM) 2017 celebration held in Cross River State. Also in that occasion, the State Commissioner for Health expressed regret toward the lack of adequate number of midwives in the state explaining further that in some Local Government Areas, there are no midwives and the state is commencing the recruitment of midwives that will gradually close up that gap (Sunday et al, 2023). Therefore, this study sought to assess midwives' population and intrapartum care service provision at primary health care level in Cross River State, Nigeria.

- **Statement of Problem**

The high prevalence of maternal mortality in sub-Saharan Africa might be secondary to poor population of midwives at primary health care level. This situation may not be different from the scenario in Nigeria where only 1 in 5 births are attended to by skilled birth attendants (Ugo, 2016; National Population Commission, 2014).

During the researcher's rural posting in this programme, it was observed that most Primary Health Care facilities within that Local Government Areas lack midwives and this may be responsible for the high number of pregnant women who patronize Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) and faith based facilities. Some of the women who booked in the health facilities end up delivering at TBA and Faith based homes. Studies have shown that most of these women who have their babies in these alternative birth places ended up developing serious complications that resulted in either the death of mothers or their babies (Etuk, Itam, & Asuquo, 2000; Kucho, & Mekonnen 2017).

Since 2009, several strategies towards improving maternal and child outcomes by the government have focused on programmes that strengthen the health system by improving access and utilization of health care. These led to the introduction of programmes such as Saving One Million Lives (SOML), Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme on maternal and child health (SURE-P MCH). The MSS and the SURE-P MCH in Nigeria aimed to close the gap of inadequate population of midwives. This effort is in line with the WHO recommendation for the provision of skilled birth attendants as one of the strategies to reduce maternal mortality. However, it has been observed that the MSS and the SURE-P MCH midwives are no more available in the PHC facilities in Cross River State to the extent that some of these facilities do not have any midwife inspite of the current situation of high maternal mortality in the state.

In view of the globally acknowledged roles of midwives towards improvement of birth outcomes, coupled with the obvious lack of midwives in some PHC facilities in the study setting; little is known empirically about the population and services of midwives in the study setting; therefore, it is pertinent to assess the population and intrapartum care service provision of midwives at Primary Health Care level in Cross River State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

Makowiecka, Achadi, Izati, & Ronsmans (2008) carried out a study on midwifery provision in Indonesia and the result revealed that 10% of villages do not have a midwife but had a nurse as a midwifery provider; there is a deficit in midwife density in remote villages compared with urban areas; those assigned to remote areas are less experienced; midwives manage few births and this may compromise their capacity to maintain professional skills; over 90% of non-hospital deliveries take place in the woman's (64%) or the midwife's (28%) home; three-quarter of midwives did not make regular use of the fee exemption scheme; midwives who live in their assigned village spend more days per month on clinical work there. They concluded that adequate provider density is an important factor in effective health care and that efforts should be made to redress the imbalance in provision, but that this can only contribute to reducing maternal mortality in the context of a supportive professional environment and timely access to emergency obstetric care.

Study carried out by Nkwo, Lawani, Obu & Chinawa, (2015) on poor availability of skilled birth attendants in Primary Health Care System in Enugu, revealed that of the 208 government-owned PHC facilities selected for the study, 152 (73.1%) were found to provide perinatal care. The remaining 56 (27.9%) were not providing perinatal care. Of the facilities that were not providing perinatal services, 38 were health posts and dispensaries which were not designed to provide perinatal services whereas 18 were Health Centres with facilities for perinatal care but each was manned by a single male Community Health Extension Worker (CHEW) or Junior Community Health Extension Worker (JCHEW). Male CHEWs and JCHEWs generally avoided providing perinatal care.

There was no obstetrician or non-obstetrician physician employed in the 152 PHC clinics studied. There were only 55 non-midwife nurses comprising of general nurses and public health nurses and none of them had received competency-based midwifery training according to the ICM recommendations. No PHC facility had more than one of such nurses. The most available cadres of health care providers at the PHC level were the CHEWs and JCHEWs. Although the mean number of CHEW/JCHEW per facility was 8.1, the actual number ranged from one to 36 per

facility. The PHC facilities that were located in the local government headquarters generally had more CHEW/JCHEWs than those that were located in the more remote communities.

Another study carried out by Ugo (2016), on Strengthening Primary Health Care Services in Rural Nigeria: The Potential of Using Midwives as Skilled Birth Attendants, the result revealed that a total of 1000 primary health care facilities across the six geopolitical zones were supported by the SURE P MCH programme and provided 24 hour services which did not obtain before the programme commenced. A total of 3158 midwives were recruited and deployed between October 2012 when the programme started and 2014. There were no midwives in all facilities before October 2012. The newly engaged midwives were distributed across the 1000 facilities according to the structure where possible. A total of 597 midwives were deployed to the North-Central zone, 389 to North-East zone, 586 to North-West zone, 509 to South-East zone, 571 in South-West zone and 506 in South-South zone.

The difference in the number of births by the skilled birth attendants (the midwives deployed to the facilities supported by SURE P MCH) and the number of women now using a contraceptive method in the areas where these facilities are located were significant. The total number of antenatal care (ANC) visits were up by 42%, new ANC visits by 39% and four or more ANC visits increased by 30% after the follow-up survey. Births by skilled birth attendants were up by 56%, postnatal visits by women were also up by 33% and women using contraceptive methods increased by 66%. The skilled delivery at birth and use of contraceptive methods showed only marginal increase at follow-up for both zones. Similar patterns were observed in the North-Central zone and South-South zone. Although the number of births by skilled birth attendants fell slightly at follow up, there was still a slight increase in the number of postnatal visits in the South-South zone. Similar patterns were also recorded in the South-East and South-West zones. Although the South-West zone showed more remarkable increases in total and new ANC visits, births by skilled birth attendants, postnatal visits and number of women using contraceptive methods. In summary, p-value for all core indicators were statistically significant, with a range of 0.48 – 0.46 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, showing the intervention had a positive impact on maternal health care improvement.

Another study by Achadi et al (2007) on Midwifery Provision and Uptake of Maternity Care in Indonesia revealed that an average density of 2.2 midwives per 1000 population, 33% of births are with a health professional, and 1% by caesarean section. Having at least six midwives per 10000 population was associated with a fourfold increase in caesareans [adjusted risk ratio (RR) 4.3: 95% confidence interval (CI): 3.3–5.5] and a threefold increase in the odds of having a health professional attend the delivery [adjusted odds ratio (OR) 2.88: 95% CI: 0.96–8.70]. The assigned midwife's professional status and the duration of her service in the village were also associated with higher rates of health professionals' attendance of delivery and caesareans.

Pricillia et al (2017) conducted a study on Quality of Antenatal Care Provided by Nurse Midwives in an Urban Health Centre with Regard to Low-Risk Antenatal Mothers in India. A total of 200 low-risk mothers were enrolled in the study. There were no drop outs or lost to follow-up. The care was provided by nine nurse midwives who were qualified in general nursing and midwifery (GNM) with a median experience of 8 years. The result showed that the quality of antenatal care for all domains were above 90% except for the health education domain, which was poor with regard to breastfeeding and family planning in the enrolled 200 pregnant women. It was therefore concluded that trained nurse midwives when regularly monitored, audited and linked with reliable referral facilities can deliver good quality antenatal care.

Hsieh et al (2009) carried out a study on Midwives attendance and workload with birth mode using secondary analyses in the German health system. This study examines the association between the attendance and workload of midwives with the mode of birth outcomes in a population of low-risk women in a German multi-centre sample. Secondary analyses included a convenience sample of 999 low-risk women from the primary analyses who met the selection criterion of 'low-risk status'. The result showed that the 'attendance of midwives' and the 'workload of midwives' did not exhibit a significant association with the mode of birth. However, women who were not satisfied with the presence of midwives (OR: 2.45, 95% CI 1.54-3.95) or who did not receive supportive procedures by midwives (OR: 3.01, 95% CI 1.50-6.05) were significantly more likely to experience operative delivery. Further explanatory variables include the type of hospital, participation in childbirth preparation class, length of stay from admission to birth, oxytocin usage

and parity. Satisfaction with the presence of and supportive procedures by midwives are associated with the mode of birth.

Altigani (2012) carried out a study on the Role of the Village Midwives in Antenatal Care Services in the Sudan. The study was conducted to assess the obstetric care coverage provided by the Sudanese village midwives. Mothers and village midwives, from four villages were interviewed using structured questionnaires. A total of 130 mothers who had delivered within 6 months were included in the study. The result of the study showed that seventy per cent of these mothers contacted the village midwives at least once during their pregnancy. The average attendance was 3-8 antenatal contacts per mother. Seventy-one per cent of those who contacted the village midwives did so during the first half of pregnancy. Half of these mothers were seen in the village midwife's own home and only 20 per cent were in the mothers' homes. The village midwives demonstrated reasonable standard of knowledge and competence in various aspects of antenatal care, history taking, examination, and selection of cases for referral. They lacked adequate support and supervision, and supplies of drugs such as iron, folic acid, and chloroquine tablets.

Another study was carried out by Andrew et al (2016) on Midwifery-led Antenatal Care Models: Mapping a Systematic Review to an Evidence-based Quality Framework to identify key Components and Characteristics of Care. A systematic review of Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) of midwifery-led antenatal care models was done. Mapping and evaluation of these models characteristic to the quality maternal and newborn care (QMNC) framework using data extraction and scoring forms derived from the five framework components. Paired team members independently extracted data and conducted quality assessment using the QMNC framework and standard RCT criteria. Results indicated that from 13,050 citations initially retrieved were identified thus: 17 RCTs of midwifery-led antenatal care models from Australia (7), the UK (4), China (2), and Sweden, Ireland, Mexico and Canada (1 each). QMNC framework scores ranged from 9 to 25 (possible range 0–32), with most models reporting fewer than half the characteristics associated with quality maternity care. Description of care model characteristics was lacking in many studies, but was better reported for the intervention arms. Organization of care was the best-described component. Underlying values and philosophy of care were poorly reported. It was concluded that the QMNC framework facilitates assessment of the characteristics of antenatal care

models. It is vital to understand all the characteristics of multi-faceted interventions such as care models; not only what is done but why it is done, by whom, and how this differed from the standard care package. By applying the QMNC framework, a foundation for future reports of intervention studies that is characteristics of individual models can be evaluated, and the impact of any differences appraised.

A qualitative study on meeting the needs and challenges of Midwives' Role in Providing Nutritional Advice during Pregnancy was carried out by Jamila, Heather & Moira (2017). The study explored the Australian midwives' role in the provision of nutrition advice. Little is known about their perceptions of this role, the influence of the model of care, and the barriers and facilitators that may influence them providing quality nutrition advice to pregnant women. Semi-structured telephone interviews were undertaken with a subsample (n=16) of the members of the Australian College of Midwives who participated in an online survey about midwives' nutrition knowledge, attitudes, and their confidence in providing nutrition advice during pregnancy. Thematic descriptive analysis was used to analyze the data. Midwives believed they have a vital role in providing nutrition advice to pregnant women in the context of health promotion. However, this was not reflected in the advice many of them provided, which in many accounts was passive and medically directed. The extent and efficacy of their role appeared to be challenged by many structural barriers. Midwives suggested facilitators that may assist in overcoming these challenges such as the need for assistance, support, and guidance to provide holistic nutrition advice that assists women to achieve healthy pregnancies.

Lohmann, Mattern & Ayerle (2018) carried out a study on Midwives' Perceptions of Women's Preferences Related to Midwifery Care in Germany: A Focus Group Study. The results revealed that Midwives in Germany felt that high-quality midwifery care is not fully realized. In hospital, midwives have to care for 3 to 4 labouring women at the same time and are faced with doctors' expectations that labour and birth be as short as possible. Thus, midwives are enormously pressed for time, severely overstretched and unsatisfied with their work. This is captured in one of the midwives' statement thus: "there is simply a lot to be improved upon, actually, the quality of care I want to offer but I am unable to live up to. That cuts me to the quick when I go home and realize

that I have cared for three, four women at the same time. This cannot be uplifting. It is not fulfilling”.

A study carried out by Tegbar et al (2017) on Quality of Midwife-provided Intrapartum Care in Amhara Regional State, Ethiopia, utilized a total of 150 midwives and 56 health facilities. The result revealed that for performance assessments 16.5% of midwives were incompetent, 72.4% were competent, and 11.1% were outstanding in providing routine intrapartum care. Forty-five midwives were observed while managing 54 obstetric and newborn complications and 41 (91%) of them were rated competent. Inventory of resources found that the proportion of facilities with more than 75% of the items in each category was 32.6% for drugs, 73.1% for equipment, 65.4% for supplies, 47.9% for infection prevention materials, and 43.6% for records and forms. Opportunities for performance improvement were inadequate, with 31.3% reporting emergency obstetric and newborn care training, and 44.7% quarterly or more frequent supportive supervision. Health centres fared worse in provider competence, physical resources, and quality improvement practices except for supportive supervision visits and in-service training.

Shimoda, Leshabari, Horiuchi, Shimpuku & Tachiro (2015) carried out a qualitative survey of Midwives' intrapartum monitoring process and management resulting in emergency referrals in Tanzania. The interviews were conducted at one hospital and one health center in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania's largest city. Eleven participants were purposively recruited and interviewed about their experiences in managing complicated intrapartum cases. After the interviews, data were analyzed using content analysis. Derived from the data were three activity phases: initial encounter, monitoring, and acting, and the result showed that midwives noticed danger signs, identified problems, revised and confirmed initial problem identification, and organized for medical intervention or referral. The timing of taking action was different for each midwife and depended on the nature of the prolonged and obstructed labor case. For the majority of midwives, the processing of assessments and judgments was brief and without reflection, and only a few midwives took time to continue to monitor the labor after the initial identification of problems and before taking actions. It was therefore agreed that to make a final judgment that the labor was becoming prolonged or obstructed, midwives should consider taking time to review and synthesize all their findings.

Davies & Iredale (2006) carried out a study on an exploration of midwives' perceptions about their role. The objective for this work was to gain an understanding of how midwives perceive their role, with particular emphasis on the provision of intrapartum care. A qualitative study using focus group methodology. Seven focus groups were held with midwives (n = 48) from maternity units in Mid and South Wales. Four main themes emerged from the data; these were: essential midwifery functions in the intrapartum period, relinquishing aspects of the midwives' role, midwives' views of how they are perceived by others and the experience of midwives working in the NHS. The main midwifery role in the provision of intrapartum care was perceived as ensuring safe outcomes for both mother and baby, along with building of trust, supportive relationships with women and their birth partners. However, it appeared that midwives' autonomy was restricted, not only by regulation, but also by the organizational systems of the NHS. By implications for practice, consideration should be given to lessening the constraints around midwifery practice and increasing autonomy.

Declercq, Belanoff & Sakala (2019) studied Intrapartum Care and Experiences of Women with Midwives Versus Obstetricians in the Listening to Mothers in California Survey. The analysis was based on 1421 of the 2539 participants who identified a midwife or obstetrician as their attendant at a vaginal birth. A bivariate analysis of demographic, attitudinal, and intrapartum variables was conducted. A multivariable model included socio-demographic and attitudinal variables as covariates. Bivariate analyses found significant socioeconomic differences by type of intrapartum care provider, with women in California attended by midwives more likely to be well educated and privately insured than women attended by obstetricians. Women with midwife birth attendants were less likely to report experiencing various intrapartum medical interventions, less likely to experience pressure to have epidural analgesia, and more likely to report that staff encouraged the woman's decision making. Adjusted odds ratios found that women with midwives were less likely to experience medical interventions, including attempted labor induction; labor augmentation; and use of pain medications, epidural analgesia, and intravenous fluids; and less likely to report pressure to have labor induction or epidural analgesia. Women cared for by midwives were more likely to experience any non-pharmacologic pain relief measures and nitrous oxide and to agree that hospital staff encouraged their decision making. Using women's own reports of their care experiences and adjusting for possible differences in women's attitudes and case mix, we found (it

was found out) that midwives' care of women who had vaginal births was associated with reduced use of medical interventions and increased women's decisional attitude during labor and birth.

Chabeli, Malesele & Nolte (2017) studied a conceptual analysis of best practice during intrapartum care. The purpose was to explore the meaning of the concept of best practice within the context of intrapartum care. The concept of best practice was analyzed using Wilson's method of concept analysis. Data saturation was reached at 117 definitions and uses of the concept of best practice. The definitions and uses of the concept of best practice listed in column one were read repeatedly. Common and similar patterns of words were highlighted. Grouping of common attributes and connotations occurred in column two and further deductive analysis and synthesis occurred in column three where derived essential attributes of the concept of best practice were categorized. Three broad categories emerged, namely (1) values as antecedents of best practice; (2) A three-phased interactive integrative cyclic process of best practice; (phase one: awareness; phase two: need analysis and interactive process; phase three: consolidation); and (3) Desired outcomes of best practice, with resultant theoretical definition of the concept best practice during intra-partum care. Theoretical validity was attained through 117 sources used. It was recommended that the results of the concept analysis of best practice should be used to develop a model to facilitate best practice during intra-partum care.

Tharamba (2015) studied post-natal experience of women with midwives during labour at Meru level 5 hospital, Kenya. Purposive sampling was used to select fifteen participants from the post-natal women who met the inclusion criteria for the study. Interviews were used to gather information from the participants, after which it was recorded with their consent. The following were the study findings: that some women in labour are physically and psychologically abused, they lack continuity of care, they are not prepared on what to expect during labour, they are never informed of findings after being examined, they do not establish a relationship with the caregivers, they feel that it is necessary to persevere despite the pain and finally it is fine to deliver while being watched by other women in labour. Despite those feelings, many of the participants said they were satisfied with the care received. However, it was concluded that there is need to adjust hospital policies to support the use of interventions proven to be of benefit to women during childbirth, and develop approaches that ensure changes in midwifery practice.

- **Objectives of the study**

This study sought to assess midwives' population and intrapartum care service provision at Primary Health Care level in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. What is the socio-demographic data of midwives in Cross River State?
2. What are the intrapartum services provided by midwives in PHC facilities in Cross River State?
3. To what extent does midwives' population influence intrapartum care service provision at Primary Health Care level in Cross River State?

- **Research Hypothesis**

There is no statistical significant difference between midwives' population and intra-partum care service provision at PHC in Cross River State

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Design**

The research design for the study is descriptive survey design; where the researcher describes the status of affairs as they exist (Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim & Ekuri, 2004). This is a method of collecting information by means of interviews and administering questionnaires. The rationale for using this design is that it allows in-depth study of the subject matter and it is suitable to describe attitudes, views or opinions and behaviour patterns of people. Therefore, the researcher described affairs as they were factual. This design is chosen on the premise that the manifestations of the variable under study had already taken place before the researcher embarked on the study. This type of design is possible when human subjects are used in real situations and the researcher comes in after the effects. This study will report its findings through coding, classification, analysis, comparison and interpretation of the data collected.

- **Study population/Sample**

The target population for this study involved all midwives working at Primary Health Care facilities in Cross River State. The study population is seventy (70) midwives. The study adopted a census sampling procedure for the quantitative approach.

- **Instrument For Data Collection**

The instrument used for data collection was the “Midwives Population and Intrapartum Service Questionnaire (MPISQ)”.

FINDINGS

Research question 1: What is the socio-demographic data of midwives in Cross River State?

Table 1 shows that, there were no male midwives as at the time of this study in the various sample areas, while the female dominated all the PHCs with the highest number 100%. This therefore implies that among the sample respondents, none of the centres have male midwives. The age of midwives within the age of 27-35years is higher with 42.8%, followed by those within 36-45 years of age 40.1%, 46-55 has 15.7% and then those in 56 years and above 1.4%.

The result of midwives’ marital status shows that majority of the midwives 57(81.4%) are married, 9(12.9%) of them are single while 4(5.7%) are widows. The professional qualification of the midwives shows that those with RN/RM are more with the highest percentage of 81.4%, followed by those with BNSc 12.9%, while those with RM only have 5.7%. Also, the result of midwives’ years of working experience reveals that those within the range of 11-20 (55.7%) indicated having more experience, followed by those within 1-10 (30.0%), those within 31-35 years have 8.6% while 21-30 years have 5.7%. However, the implication of this result could be as a result of the number of midwives present at the PHCs at the time of this study.

TABLE 1: Socio-demographic data of midwives in Cross River State, Nigeria

S/N	Variable	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender		
	Male	-	-
	Female	70	100
2.	Age		
	27-35	30	42.8

	36-45	28	40.1
	46-55	11	15.7
	56 and above	1	1.4
	Total	70	100
3.	Marital Status of Midwives		
	Single	9	12.9
	Married	57	81.4
	Divorced	-	-
	Widowed	4	5.7
	Total	70	100
4.	Professional Qualification		
	RN/ RM	57	81.4
	RM only	4	5.7
	BNSc	9	12.9
	Total	70	100
5.	Years of Experience		
	1-10	21	30
	11-20	39	55.7
	21-30	4	5.7
	31-35	6	8.6
	Total	70	100
6.	Professional Rank		
	NS	28	40.0
	SNO	16	22.9
	PNO	10	14.3
	ACNS	4	5.7
	CNO and above	12	17.1
	Total	70	100
7.	Nature of Employment		
	Government	68	97.1
	Volunteer	-	-
	Contract	2	2.9
	Total	70	100

SNS = *Sympathetic* Nervous System
 SNO = Senior Nursing officer
 RN = Registered Nurse
 ACNS = Addiction clinical nurse specialist

PNO = Principal Nursing Officer
 RM = Registered Midwife
 SNO = Senior Nursing officer
 CNO = Chief Nursing Officer

Further, the result of the professional rank of the midwives shows that those with NS rank 28(40.0%) are the highest in the sample area, followed by SNS & SNO 16(22.9%), PNS /PNO 10(14.3%) those with SNS professional rank 9(12.9%), ACNS/ACNO have least number 4(5.7%), while those with CNO and above are 12(17.1%). The implication of this result shows that among the professional rank, NS have the highest number while ACNS/ACNO are the least number in the professional rank, while 68(97.1%) of the midwives found at the different PHCs are government employed, 2(2.9%) were mentor midwives on contract and none of them indicated being volunteer staff.

Research question 2: What is the overall population of midwives in Primary Health Care in Cross River State?

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics of midwives population in the study area; the result shows that Ikom has the highest number of midwives 11(15.7%), followed by Yala 8(11.4%), Calabar Municipal have 7(10.0%), Akamkpa and Obudu have 6(8.6%), Bekwarra, Obanliku have 5(7.1%) each, Boki and Yakurr have 4(5.7%) each, Abi, Obubra and Odukpani have 3(4.3%) each, Ogoja has 2(2.9%), Akpabuyo, Biase and Calabar South have 1(1.4%) each, while Bakassi and Etung have none. Making a total number of seventy (70) midwives in all the PHC facilities of Cross River State.

TABLE 2: Distribution of population of midwives in PHCs (n=70)

Population/Location	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)M
Abi	3	4.3
Akamkpa	6	8.6
Akpabuyo	1	1.4
Bakkasi	-	-
Bekwara	5	7.1
Biase	1	1.4
Boki	4	5.7
Cal. South	1	1.4
Cal. Municipal	7	10.0
Etung	-	-
Ikom	11	15.7
Obanliku	5	7.1
Obubra	3	4.3
Obudu	6	8.6
Odukpani	3	4.3
Ogoja	2	2.9
Yakurr	4	5.7
Yala	8	11.4
Total	70	100

Research question three: What are the intrapartum services provided by midwives in PHC facilities in Cross River State?

TABLE 3: Description of Type of Intrapartum Services (n=70)

Intra-Partum care	Always	Most times	sometimes	Not at all
History taking	16 (22.6%)	36 (51.4%)	18 (25.7%)	-
Vital signs check	11 (15.7%)	52 (74.3%)	6 (8.6%)	1 (1.4%)
Vaginal examination	12 (17.1%)	38 (54.3%)	20 (28.6%)	-
Abdominal examination	15(21.42%)	13(18.58%)	42(60%)	-
Use of partograph	5 (7.1%)	21 (30.0%)	44 (62.9%)	-
Catheterization	6 (8.6%)	8 (11.4%)	54 (77.1%)	2 (2.9%)
Giving/suturing of episiotomy	6 (8.6%)	11 (15.7%)	52 (74.3%)	1(1.4%)
Provision of Emergency- Obstetric care	13 (18.6%)	11 (15.7%)	46 (65.7%)	-
Immediate care of the new born	18(25.71%)	19(27.14%)	33(47.15%)	-
Referrals	12 (17.1%)	43 (61.4%)	15 (21.4%)	-

Table 3 showed the descriptive statistics of type of services provided by the midwives in PHCs with respect to intra-partum care in Cross River State. During the **intra-partum care**, the result in table 3 revealed that 50-80% of midwives sometimes do the following services: catheterization, suturing, use of partograph, provision of emergency obstetric and immediate care of the newborn, while services such has referrals 63.4%, vaginal examination 54.3%, vital signs check 74.3% and history taking 51.3% of respondents is done most of the time. The implication of this result is that

most of the services are delivered some of the time as a result of inadequate number of midwives present at the PHCs.

Test of hypothesis

There is no significant influence between midwives population and intrapartum care service provision. The independent variable is midwives' population while the dependent variable is intrapartum care service provision. and it is grouped into PHC facilities that have high number of midwives population, that is, three (3) and above and those PHC facilities that have low number of midwives population, that is, below three (3) midwives in each PHCs in Cross River State. The dependent, intrapartum care service provision is a continuous variable. To test this hypothesis, the independent t-test analysis was applied to test the data at 0.05 level of significance and 68 degrees of freedom. The result is presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4: Independent t-test analysis of the difference between midwives population and intrapartum care service provision in Cross River State, Nigeria. N= 70

Mid-wives groups	no of PHCs	n	Mean	S.D	t-cal	p-value
3&Above Midwives in PHCs	(1)	7	36.42	1.27		
					27.559*	.000
1-2 Midwives in PHCs	(43)	63	18.26	3.57		

Significant at $P < .05$ $df=68$ Critical $t= 1.980$

From Table 4, the highest score of intrapartum care service delivery a respondent is supposed to score is 40, while the lowest score is 10. PHCs with 3 and above mid-wives was one (1) and have 36.42 and 1.27 mean and standard deviations respectively, while PHCs with at least 1-2 mid-wives is forty three (43) and had 18.26 and 3.57 mean and standard deviations score respectively. The

result showed that the t-test calculated of 27.559 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.980. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence between midwives' population and intrapartum care service provision was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld. This implies that there is a significant influence between midwives population and intrapartum care service provision in PHCs in Cross River State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The result on the overall population of midwives at PHC level of Cross River State revealed gross inadequate midwives' population in all the Local Government Areas in the State. The analysis shows that the entire State had only seventy midwives in all the eighteen LGAs which is generally small and below the recommendation of World Health Organization. It was obvious that disparity exist between statistics on midwives' population obtained from State Primary Health Care Agency and what was obtained from the PHC facilities. So this reduced population created differences between the midwives/patient relationship which invariably reduced quality of care given to the patient. The result also revealed that majority of the PHCs in the State do not have any midwives at all. Out of two hundred and two primary health centres in Cross River State, only forty-four PHCs have midwives while one hundred and fifty-eight PHCs have no midwife at all, only one out of the forty-four PHCs have seven midwives, eight PHCs have two midwives each and the majority thirty-six PHCs have only one midwife.

The result simply implies that without adequate midwives' population to provide quality ANC services to pregnant women, good pregnancy outcome may not be achieved because midwives have the skills and are responsible for the care of a woman during pregnancy. The population of midwives also determine the quality of intrapartum care. This simply implies that the PHC facilities that had required midwives provide quality services than those that had one midwife and due to inadequate number of midwives, pregnant women prefer other alternative birthing places because they were not satisfied with the services provided in such facilities. Also, there was a relationship between midwives' population and postpartum service provision as the findings implies that without adequate midwives' population to provide quality postpartum services to

women and their new born babies, postnatal complications may arise. This is because midwives have the skill and are totally responsible for the care of women and their new born.

This agrees with Altigani (2012) who examined the Role of the Village Midwives in Antenatal Care Services in the Sudan and the result showed that the village midwives demonstrated reasonable standard of knowledge and competence in various aspects of antenatal care, history taking, examination, and selection of cases for referral.

The findings also corroborate with the study carried out by Nyasulu (2013) on Midwife's role of Community-based, Family-centred Postnatal care. The study posited that midwives are, and have always been, the backbone of maternity services care. By virtue of this position, midwives should take the lead in restructuring maternity care.

The study also agreed with Bernis et al (2013) who carried out a study on Skilled attendants for pregnancy, childbirth and postnatal care. The findings shows that Skilled attendants need to be supported by a health system providing a legal and policy infrastructure, an effective referral system and the supplies that are necessary for effective care. A skilled attendant providing skilled care will help achieve the goals of reducing both maternal and child mortality. Health care professionals as individual practitioners, leaders and informers have an important role in making this a reality.

- **Implications of this study to midwifery practice**

The findings of this study imply that there is gross shortage of midwives population in all primary health care facilities in Cross River State. Due to inadequate number of midwives in primary health care facilities the findings revealed that, task shifting, poor quality of care was practiced, where most of the services midwives were supposed to render were being provided by other health workers who do not have midwifery training and adequate skills. This shifting of significant midwifery task is perceived to contribute significantly to maternal morbidity and mortality in Cross River State. In this study, majority of participants are of the opinion that maternal mortality rate in Cross River State can never reduce without increasing midwives' population in all the PHC facilities.

- **Summary/Conclusion**

The population of midwives at PHC level in Cross River State is grossly inadequate. This deprives the women of child bearing age of their right to be attended to by competent midwives as

recommended by ICM and WHO. This implies that the women particularly in rural areas where PHCs are the only source of modern health care facilities, are exposed to the risk of morbidity and mortality.

- **Recommendations**

1. The government should employ more midwives as a way to improve midwives' population at Primary Health care level in the State.
2. The government should focus on providing basic amenities in the community for quality maternity services at Primary Health care level in the State
3. Policy makers should formulate policies that will help promote midwifery workforce at the Primary Health care level in the State.
4. Midwives should embark on advocacy to the government and non-governmental bodies on the need to improve midwives' population which will lead to improved service delivery in PHC level in the State
5. The presence of midwives in State Primary Health Care Development Agency should be strengthened.
6. Nursing and midwifery council should review the policy to establish community midwifery in Cross River State where more midwives will be trained and automatically employed to PHC level in the State.
7. Scholarship schemes should be developed to sponsor students for pre-service midwifery.

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